

National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group Meeting, 28th June 2024, 12pm

Minutes

OpenAIRE opened the meeting with a presentation on the Delivery of the National OA Monitor, Ireland which contains 5 Monitors:

- Researchers
- Research Funding Organisations
- National Monitor
- Research Performing Organisations
- Institutional repositories

They outlined the project Specification Requirements which were met and the UI/UX improvements which were implemented in the pilot phase, ongoing work on Data Quality Enhancement and highlighted the need for further engagement and training.

Following their presentation OpenAIRE stepped out of the meeting and the Advisory group continued to the discussion on the next steps for the National Open Access Monitor.

- All agreed that the pilot phase has been successful and exceeded expectations.
- The group suggested that for more widespread utilisation of the Monitor, it requires greater promotion.
- Noted that it will take at least a year if not more for the monitor to be embedded and used by institutions and funders and therefore more time is needed for feedback and the pilot phase
- All agreed that the pilot phase of the monitor should be extended, in order for it to become an integral part of the higher education research infrastructure

Decision: Continue the pilot phase of the monitor for a further 6 months using existing funding

Action: IReL to prepare report outlining our recommendations, 6-month extension of existing contract, followed by a further 2-year phase to embed the Monitor. This will be shared with the group before sending to NORF.